

IMPACT

UNDERSTANDING CHARPY IMPACT TESTING
OF COMPOSITE MATERIALSby
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This paper reports a series of detailed impact and slow rate tests using Charpy notched and unnotched specimens aimed at understanding the test result in terms of both the material structure and properties, and the test geometry. The framework developed allows prediction of the failure mode and estimation of the potential energy absorption based on the laminate material properties. The laminates studied were all commercial glass fibre reinforced laminates with varying reinforcement geometries which exhibited a range of failure modes and absorbed energies.

INTRODUCTION

One of the many evaluations necessary for any new material is to assess its toughness. Impact tests are an established method for measuring the "toughness" of materials with the resultant absorbed energy data referred to as the impact strength. It is not clear how this 'strength' measured for an arbitrary short beam specimen is related to the properties of the constituent materials, to the normal strength data or to the service conditions to be experienced. Because of the potential number of composite materials that can be produced it is important that simple frameworks and predictive models exist for the specimen performance in impact tests and under service impact loads.

One series of impact tests undertaken within a larger study [1] was for commercially available glass fibre reinforced laminates which had a range of fibre reinforcement geometries and volume fractions. The reinforcements included aligned fibres (tested in both the longitudinal and transverse directions), mats, a fabric and a crossply. The materials were tested with loading directions parallel and perpendicular to the plane of the sheet, and in both the notched and unnotched conditions. To assist in the interpretation of the failure modes, slow rate flexure tests using identical specimens and test geometries were also conducted. Analysis of the failure modes and recorded data was undertaken using data measured at the slow loading rate for the tensile, compression and shear strengths of the laminates.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Materials and Specimens

Several materials were selected from the range of glass fibre reinforced laminates manufactured by Permal (Gloucester) Ltd. Apart from the wet lay-up mat materials, the materials were prepared using the pre-preg method which gave a good quality, consistent laminate. The materials selected included two mats, a weave, a crossply and a fully aligned reinforcement.

The weave material was a fine balanced weave/epoxy (manufacturer's designation 22FE) with a layer thickness of approximately 0.3 mm, a resin layer between plies varying between 0.1 to 0.3 mm, and effectively zero porosity. The mat/epoxy (33ME) was randomly orientated within the plane with a very layered structure. There was a small degree of porosity within the resin but the fibre bundles were well impregnated. In contrast the lower volume fraction mat/polyester (33MP) had smaller, less well impregnated fibre bundles, and a less well layered structure. This material had significant resin and strand porosity. The crossply/epoxy (XE6) and aligned/epoxy (XE5) materials had a fine protective surface weave on both faces. The aligned fibres were within a few degrees in each layer. There was no resin rich layer between layers nor was there any porosity. The fully aligned material was tested with the fibres along (designated 'longitudinal') and across ("transverse") the specimen axis.

(a)

(b) Direct scissor shear test

(c) Four point loading configuration

Figure 1 Specimen and loading configurations

The standard samples, 6.4 mm x 6.4 mm x 45 mm long, were prepared using a diamond slitting wheel except that for .25" (=6.35 mm) thick laminates they were tested at the original thickness. This method was used also to prepare direct scissor shear, compression prisms and long beam flexure specimens. Notch geometries, shown at the centre line cross-section in Figure 1a, were cut with an extra thin slitting blade, and sharpened using a jeweller's saw. Specimens were cut so that the load was applied perpendicular (\perp) and parallel (\parallel) to the plane of the sheet. Restriction on space has resulted in only the perpendicular specimen data being reported in detail in this paper.

Test Methods

Impact tests were undertaken using a Tensometer miniature Charpy impact machine (impact velocity = 2.44 m/s). Interchangeable tups with input energies ranging from 0.042 J to 2.71 J were available. The tup used was chosen so that the absorbed energy was between 0.3 and 0.7 of the input energy. The standard loading arrangement had a span of 38.5 mm with a pair of central loading noses each with a 3 mm radius and a central span of 6.5 mm. This configuration is shown in Figure 1c. Adaptors were produced to replace these central noses by a single nose to give a standard 3-point loading geometry.

Duplicates of these loading configurations were used on a screw driven Instron test machine at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. Static tests for the direct shear stress were measured using the compression scissor specimen shown in Figure 1b. This configuration was preferred to the short beam interlaminar shear test as the latter is not suitable for materials with relatively high shear strengths when prior compression failures at the loading points can occur. The results were corrected for the stress concentration due to the notches as given in [2]. Other support tests were performed in flexure on long beams, and in compression on small prisms in the axial direction. Samples were sectioned, polished and examined microscopically to assess their initial quality and to analyse their failure mode.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Impact and slow rate test results

In Table 1 are given the impact energies per unit cross-section area for the three and four point unnotched specimens, the straight notched specimen and also the unnotched specimen under three point loading at a slow rate. The energy absorbed in the slow rate test was obtained from the area under the load-displacement curve. The most obvious trends are that four point tests generally absorbed more energy than three point tests, that more energy was absorbed in the impact test than in the slow rate tests, and that the straight notched results could be as high as the unnotched results as shown by the notch sensitivity ratio in the final column.

Table 1
Absorbed Energy and Notch Sensitivity

Laminate	Energy Absorbed (kJ/m^2)				Straight Notch Sensitivity
	Slow rate 3-pt	3-pt	Impact Rate 4-pt	Notched	
Weave	137	175	214	146	.83
Mat/epoxy	43	143	225	114	.80
Mat/polyester	32	81	97	54	.67
Crossply	138	227	214	229	1.01
Longitudinal	157	360	609	413	1.15
Transverse	3.2	28	26	8.6	0.31

The supporting data for the shear strength, the axial compression strength, the flexural (long beam) strength and modulus measured at a slow rate are given in Table 2. This table of data compared well with manufacturer's strength and stiffness data which is not reproduced here.

It should be noted that, usefully, the laminates are ranked in the same order by the absorbed energy as measured in all three impact tests and in the slow rate test, as shown by the data in Table 1. The results for the aligned material which recorded the lowest value in the transverse direction and the highest value for the longitudinal direction shows the much higher anisotropy found for the impact performance than recorded for flexural modulus.

Table 2
Laminate properties measured at a slow rate

Laminate	Glassfibre Volume Fraction	Shear Strength MN/m^2	Compression Strength MN/m^2	Flexure Strength MN/m^2	Flexural Modulus GN/m^2
Weave	0.38	22.9	126	236	15.9
Mat/epoxy	0.42	42.9	350	334	14.8
Mat/polyester	0.20	22.5	174	146	9.7
Crossply	0.61	54.2	480	761	30.4
Longitudinal	0.61	40.9	608	1021	35.0
Transverse	0.61	37.7	131	101	16.6

Finally in Table 3 is given the analysis of the slow rate 3-point beam tests for the flexural modulus, the flexural and interlaminar stress at the maximum load and the work done to fail the specimen. The work done has been analysed for the total area under the curve (ie the work to separate or fail the specimen (WS), the work to the peak load (WP) and the work to the limit of linear behaviour (WL)). Both WP and WL are given as a fraction of WS. The latter is assumed to be the energy absorbed to first damage. The corresponding load - displacement curves are given in Figure 2.

Table 3
Analysis of slow rate short beam tests

Laminate	Apparent Flexural Modulus GN/m ²	Maximum Flexural Stress MN/m ²	Maximum Shear Stress MN/m ²	Work to Separate kJ/m ²	WL WS	WP WS
Weave	10.3	227	19	137	.05	.10
Mat/epoxy	7.7	303	37	43	.47	.66
Mat/polyester	7.3	170	14	32	.03	.58
Crossply	19.5	640	52	138	.15	.41
Longitudinal	22.1	710	53	157	.15	.50
Transverse	14.3	79	6	32	.24	.47

Fractographic observations - Unnotched specimens

In Figure 3 are shown the perpendicular direction (\perp) specimens tested in the unnotched condition at the impact and slow rates respectively. The weave material failed by a compression/shear buckle on a line from the central loading nose to one of the end supports. Buckling of individual fabric layers initiated local splits and delaminations which in some cases propagated to the end of the specimen. The damage was similar at both loading rates with the damage more developed at the slow rate. The mat/epoxy failed in tension with damage limited to a short length of specimen. In contrast the nominally similar mat/polyester laminate while occasionally failing in a simple tensile mode, more frequently failed by disintegrating on the plane between centre and end supports. The disintegration was greatest at the impact rate.

Figure 2 Typical load - displacement curves for each laminate

The crossply and longitudinal specimen failed by a combination of compression and delamination. In the crossply material compression damage was limited to the outermost 0° layer on the compression face of the specimen with delamination between many 0° and 90° layers. The compression zone was largest, with a small degree of 0° tensile failure on the tensile surface, in the slow rate test. The longitudinally aligned material failed by compression and delamination failures. At slow rates only a single delamination occurred at the tip of a compression failure which covered approximately half the beam depth. Final failure was associated with this brittle, compression initiated crack. The compression failure was by a kink band with a width of only $116\text{-}160\ \mu\text{m}$, with a micro-kink band $30\ \mu\text{m}$ s wide, developing at the central loading point position, as shown in Figure 4. The transversely aligned specimen failed in tension in the bulk of the material followed by failure of the outer protective fabric.

I.

S.

Figure 3 Unnotched specimens tested at impact(I)
and slow rates(S)(x0.5)

Figure 4 Kink band on compression face above central loading point for longitudinal laminate

Some differences were observed for the parallel direction (-) tested specimens. For example the delamination, shear and disintegration failures observed were now suppressed so that the compression and/or tension failure was now more localised. The fabric specimen failed by an extensive buckle.

There were some detailed modifications to the failure mode when the 4-point loading arrangement was used. In materials with compression failures (fabric, aligned, crossply) a second normally small compression damage zone was obtained. For materials with delaminations (aligned, crossply) their number increased. Delamination failures were also obtained for some materials where they were normally absent (fabric, mat/epoxy).

- Notched Specimens

In Figure 5 are shown the impact loaded straight notch specimens. For (1) specimens the transversely aligned and both mat specimens failed by tensile failure, although one of the mat/epoxy did also delaminate on a plane remote from the notch tip. The crossply and longitudinal aligned delaminated at the notch tip and then failed as unnotched beams. The fabric material failed by compression and tension failures in the vertical plane of the notch. Tests in the in-plane direction repeated the trends observed for this direction in the unnotched beams with the suppression of delamination failures leaving materials to fail by pure tension (mats, transverse) or by compression/tension (fabric, aligned, crossply) on a narrow crack front. The chevron (TT) notched specimens were not successful in suppressing unwanted compression and shear failures. There was an increased amount of fibre pull-out for both test directions [ie (1) and (-)].

Figure 5 Straight notched specimens impact tested in the (⊥) and (-) directions

DISCUSSION

The similarity of the failure modes and energy levels observed at both test rates suggest that the full load-displacement data obtained at slow rates can be taken as a good indicator of the response at the impact rate. This assumption has been supported since by the use of a high rate servo-hydraulic test machine that enabled tests to be conducted at intermediate rates. For example, Figure 6 shows load-displacement curves for the mat/polyester laminate at 10^{-6} , 10^{-4} , 10^{-2} and 10^{-1} m/s. The flexural properties increased progressively as the test rate was increased. This assumption allows the larger data bank available at slow rates to be used in the analysis of failure modes and suggests that at laboratory impact rates, 1 to 7 m/s, the response of the specimen can be considered to be pseudo-static.

Figure 6 Load-displacement curves for mat/polyester specimens at 10^{-6} , 10^{-4} , 10^{-2} and 10^{-1} m/s displacement rate

Failure mode prediction

The fracture observations suggest that three failure modes occurred in these specimens; a tensile face flexure stress failure, a compressive face flexure stress failure and an interlaminar shear stress failure.

The flexural (σ) and shear (τ) stresses in a three point loaded beam are given by:-

$$\sigma = 3Pl/2bd^3, \quad \tau = 3P/4bd \quad (1)$$

where l = test span, P = applied load and b , d are the specimen breadth and depth respectively.

The ratio of the shear stress to flexural stress at a failure load P is given by $(\tau/\sigma) = d/2l$, which equals 12 for the geometry used in these tests. So that failure in shear will occur if $\tau_f < \sigma_f d/2l$, where σ_f and τ_f are the respective failure stresses. For σ_f the lower of the tensile and compressive failure strengths is taken. If τ_f is greater than $\sigma_f d/2l$ then a flexural failure will occur, initiated by the face with the lower strength. The stress concentration at the loading point may require the compression strength to be somewhat greater than the tensile strength for them to have equal probability.

The probability of these different failure modes occurring can be visualised using the ternary diagram shown in Figure 7. If the compressive strength equals C , the tensile strength T and the shear strength S ; and their sum is set equal to Z then

$$C + T + 12S = Z \quad (2)$$

where the shear strength has been increased by the factor 12 which is the

ratio between flexural and shear stresses calculated above.

These strength values can be plotted on the ternary diagram by re-writing the equation as

$$\frac{C}{Z} + \frac{T}{Z} + \frac{12S}{Z} = 1 \quad (3)$$

Figure 7 Failure mode prediction plots for commercial laminates

The appropriate individual laminate strengths (ie shear, tension, compression) values for each of these laminates have been used to plot the datapoint for each laminate in Figure 7. It is of course important that the data refer to the same conditions as to be predicted (eg same rate, temperature or pre-conditioning). The data for this analysis have been taken from Table 2 with the long beam flexure strengths taken as the tensile failure strength, as these were similar to the manufacturer's tensile strength data.

In Figure 7(a) for (⊥) orientation specimens several materials are

plotted close to the shear-compression failure zone boundary. This boundary is difficult to define as compression failures in these materials by local buckling mechanisms appear to be assisted by shear and indentation stresses. In fact a similar failure can be generated by an indentation load on a fully supported specimen.

In Table 4 the predicted and observed failure modes are compared for both the (\perp) and (-) orientation specimens. There is a good level of agreement for both specimen orientations. For the in plane (-) loaded specimens the measured shear strengths were very high except for the longitudinal specimen, so that the predictive model can be reduced to a binary model only considering the relative tensile and compressive strengths. This model is shown in Figure 7(b). The longitudinal (-) direction specimen was plotted in Figure 7(a), because the shear strength was only slightly greater than the (\perp) direction specimen. The increased strength may be due to the presence of the surface weave which is now in shear for this specimen orientation. In addition any weak plane due to slight misalignment between laminae is eliminated.

Table 4

Comparison of predicted and experimentally observed failure modes

Laminate	Experimental		Predicted	
	(\perp)	(-)	(\perp)	(-)
Weave	Compression	Compression	Compression	Compression
Mat/epoxy	Tension	Tension	Tension	Tension
Mat/polyester	Tension	Tension	Tension	Tension
Crossply	Compression	Compression/ shear	Compression	Compression
Longitudinal	Compression	Compression/ shear	Compression	Shear
Transverse	Tension	Tension	Tension	Tension

The model can also be used to interpret the notch sensitivity in Table 1. In [1] it was found for many materials that delamination at the notch tip occurred for materials where the tensile strength was 11.2 times greater than the shear strength. This ratio agrees well with theoretical predictions [3] for notch tip delamination. For four laminates; weave (10.3), mat/epoxy (7.8), mat/polyester (6.5) and transverse (2.7) the ratio (given in brackets) suggest transverse crack propagation rather than delamination, so that the notch embrittlements recorded in Table 1 are expected. The notch sensitivity varies almost directly with the value of the ratios given above. For two materials, longitudinal (25) and crossply (14) delamination at the tip is predicted and observed. On delamination the specimen is reduced to a thinner unnotched beam which can be analysed according to Figure 7a with the shear stress factor increased from 12 to 24, if the original notch was cut to half the beam depth. This makes further delamination unlikely unless the shear strength is very low.

Similarly the four point bend test has a shear stress ratio of 10 so that delamination is now more likely in agreement with the fracture observations.

Application of the model to the impact test requires the basic tensile, compressive and shear strengths at that rate. Compared to the slow rate data it appears that both the compressive strength, possibly associated with a stiffer matrix material at the high rate providing improved support against microbuckling of the fibres, and the tensile strength [4] increase with increased test rate. These changes coupled with a probable smaller increase or even decreased shear strength at the impact rate suggests that there would be increased delamination failures and reduced compression failures compared to the slow rate failure. These changes can be observed by comparing the longitudinal specimens in Figure 3 tested at both rates.

Load, displacement and energies prediction

Following prediction of the failure modes it is possible to consider the likely load-displacement response of the specimen. In Figure 8 are shown the response for single failure modes. However, frequently a combined failure mode is obtained which involves two or more basic failure modes. This is illustrated at the most complex level by the combined failure in Figure 8, where a local compression, microbuckling occurs at A followed by a stable buckling phase until an interlaminar failure occurs at B. This is followed by elastic reloading of the delaminated beams to C, where further compression damage occurs prior to the final tension failure at D. This type of curve mirrors well the curve for the longitudinal specimen in Figure 2.

Figure 8 Schematic load - displacement curves for different failure modes

In order to check the fibre failure stress for specimens failing finally in tension but with prior compression damage, it was found [1] necessary to analyse the effect of this prior damage on the position of the neutral axis. The fraction of the beam cross-section failing in compression was measured and assumed to maintain a stable stress equal to the stress

for the initial failure (ie equivalent to the linear limit stress). Using this information to estimate the resultant re-positioning of the specimen neutral axis, it was possible to prove that final failure occurred at the expected fibre failure stress.

This complex stress pattern complicates the detailed comparisons of the flexural and shear stresses at the maximum load in Table 3 with the corresponding ultimate strength data. It is not possible to undertake a detailed analysis in this paper as space is restricted, so a comparison of energy absorption has been based on the measured slow rate properties in the actual test configuration.

In Table 5 are given predictions for the energy absorbed at different stages of the test. In each case the prediction is based on an assessment of the properties at the macro level. This avoids the need to know interface pull out strengths etc for predictions based on micro mechanisms of energy absorption. The elastic limit prediction (=WL) is based on the strain energy in the flexure specimen ($= \sigma_L^2/18E'$) at the linear limit stress (σ_L). Similarly the energy at the peak load (=WP) is given by the strain energy at the peak stress ($= \sigma_p^2/18E'$). This prediction tends to underestimate the energy for compressive failure cases where extra energy is absorbed during the "stable" compression/shear stage. Similar difficulties apply to the total energy prediction (=WS) which is based on progressive tensile failure of each layer in the laminate and does not allow fully for the buckling type failures ($= \sigma_p^2/6E'$). In each case the modulus of the specimen (E') used in the prediction is reduced due to the additional deflection that occurs due to shear in short beams. This effect is larger for composite materials than isotropic materials because of their larger ratio of flexural-to-shear moduli. This effect predicts [1] a 37% reduction in the flexural modulus for the longitudinal specimen, which compares well with the 40% difference between the moduli in Table 2 and 3. Test machine and loading point indentation can further reduce the apparent material stiffness [1].

The agreement for WL is good which is to be expected as the response is linear at this point, whereas for WP agreement is less satisfactory when compression/shear failures were recorded. For WS good agreement was obtained for both tensile (eg transverse, mat/polyester) and compression-shear (eg crossply, longitudinal) failures. The WS prediction gave poor agreement for the weave and mat/epoxy laminates.

Table 5

Comparison of measured and predicted energy absorptions (kJ/m^2)

Laminate	WL		WP		WS	
	Expt	Theory	Expt	Theory	Expt	Theory
Weave	6.1	5.7	13.9	10.7	137.	32.1
Mat/epoxy	20.3	20.5	28.4	28.8	43.	86.6
Mat/polyester	0.9	0.6	18.5	8.47	32.	25.4
Crossply	20.6	22.3	56.7	44.9	138	134.8
Longitudinal	24.1	26.2	77.7	48.8	157	146.4
Transverse	0.8	0.8	1.54	0.94	3.2	2.82

CONCLUSIONS

The work reported in this paper has suggested that information on impact failure modes can be obtained using identical specimen and loading geometries at slow loading rates. It has been demonstrated that the data obtained are the result of the complex interaction of the test geometry and applied stresses with the anisotropic properties of the composite material under test. A particular effect of the Charpy, and Izod, geometries is that these short beams are in fact short thick beams which have high shear stresses present. These stresses result in considerable additional specimen deflection and a high chance of an interlaminar shear failure. These effects do not always exist to the same degree in service loadings, or for isotropic materials.

A model has been described which successfully predicts the failure modes for commercial laminates containing a range of reinforcement geometries. From the predicted failure modes the expected load-displacement response and associated energies can be estimated. Difficulties remain in predicting the failure stresses for compression initiated failures. To use the model at the impact test rate requires the individual tensile, compressive and shear strengths to be measured at the same rate. Techniques are available to make these measurements but it is probably more worthwhile to use the data directly in design than use it to predict the performance of a somewhat arbitrary short beam impact specimen.

Also highlighted is the difficulty of notching materials which are inherently notch insensitive. The similarity of the stress ratio for the test geometry (ie 12) and the critical flexure-to-shear strength ratio (ie 11.2) for delamination at the notch tip means that a material which fails in this test geometry, for the unnotched specimen, due to interlaminar shear will most likely be notch insensitive.

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